

10 evidence-based policy recommendations for developing citizen science

Since November 2019 the international research project CS Track has been combining traditional social-science methods with web-based and computational analytics in order to systematically survey the field of Citizen Science. Based on our findings, we have now developed a set of 10 policy recommendations which identify key issues to be addressed if we want to further support and promote participatory research in Europe. The goal of these recommendations is to suggest ways in which CS stakeholders (such as project initiators, platform managers or funding agencies) can help maximise the benefit of Citizen Science activities for individual citizens, the scientific community, and society at large. Download the full report [here](#).

The document presents 10 policy recommendations grouped into 5 categories:

- theory (i.e. the definition of Citizen Science and its position in relation to other forms of knowledge production and education)
- creation (scientific and educational outcomes, the role and weight of Citizen Science within the scientific process)
- operation (coordination and management of CS activities – training and deliberate design of learning opportunities, internal communication etc.),
- technology (accessibility of required equipment, data protection and privacy)
- value (cost and funding of CS activities, evaluation and impact assessment)

These issues were investigated on three different levels: micro, meso, and macro. Micro refers to the level of individual citizen science practitioners (e.g. project initiators and coordinators, citizen scientists), meso refers to the technical and institutional infrastructure that supports and facilitates CS activities (such as citizen science networks and platforms, science centres, online discussion forums, training for citizen scientists), and macro refers to the societal level – both in terms of impact and regarding the political and financial conditions for CS (i.e. funding programmes, policy frameworks etc.).

Download the full deliverable [here](#).

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